

1 **A web-based system for fungus disease risk assessment in greenhouses: System**
2 **development**

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9

10 **Abstract:** Nowadays, there is a great need and public concern for reduced use of hazardous
11 pesticides in horticulture and implementation of alternative approaches for rational pests and
12 diseases suppression. This goal is approached by integrating crop protection measures and non-
13 chemical measures or applying crop protection products only when needed, thus eliminating
14 unnecessary applications. In addition, preventive farm management methods such as optimal
15 management of the aerial environment in greenhouses with sufficient installed technology may
16 provide adequate disease suppression, as the grower can avoid conditions that favour pests and
17 fungus development. Aim of this study is the development of a web-based decision support
18 system (DSS) that estimates the risk for a fungi disease outbreak in a greenhouse. The disease
19 development risk assessment is based on disease models already available in the literature that
20 correlate the rate of disease development to crop microclimate conditions and cultivation
21 practices. Up to now such models were mainly used for the disease development risk assessment
22 based on past or historical data. A strong point of the work is related to the fact that the DSS
23 makes use of the outside climate forecast to predict the greenhouse microclimate conditions
24 during a set of days that will follow. Then, based on the predicted microclimate inside the
25 greenhouse the *Botrytis* disease development models are used to assess the potential risk for
26 disease development in a greenhouse tomato crop during the following days. The greenhouse
27 microclimate is estimated based on the outside weather forecast for the region of the greenhouse,
28 the greenhouse energy and vapour balance, the greenhouse control concept and methodology,
29 the climate control equipment and the greenhouse climate set points. The last part of the DSS,
30 contains a tactical and strategical tool that, according to the risk assessment, suggests climate
31 control actions to prevent fungi development for preventive and optimal disease control. Such a
32 DSS can then be included in disease management systems to assist growers to decide when to
33 proceed to a certain action in order to modify the conditions that favour the development of a
34 disease, or if necessary, when to apply the proper permitted plant protection products. In this
35 work, the development of the DSS and the results of the validation process of the microclimate
36 predicted values are presented.

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38 **Keywords:** decision support system; organic farming; *Botrytis*; microclimate management;
39 pesticides reduction; tomato; preventive farm management

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43 1. Introduction

44 Vegetable production in greenhouses is a main income source for thousands of commercial farms
45 as well as a source of key food in the diets of people all over the world. Greenhouses, however,
46 are highly specialized cropping systems. The production is being intensified, resulting in yields that
47 are double, or triple compared to open field production. Their management requires the intensive
48 use of energy, water, and other inputs. The intensification in vegetable production, in particular,
49 has resulted in a massive use of crop protection products and fertilizers, with significant impacts
50 on people and environment.

51 The last decades the use of chemicals on crops has arisen a lot of consideration against for
52 consumer's health and the protection of environment. Together with the public reaction and the
53 awareness for safe and high-quality vegetable production, the main trend and public claim is the
54 reduction of the use of chemicals or contentious inputs on crops and the need of alternative
55 approaches for rational cultivation and crop protection.

56 An increasing interest in organic greenhouse production has been shown by organic farming
57 associations, researchers, and policy makers either at a national or at a transnational level.
58 However, a very general inventory estimates the total greenhouse covered area under organic
59 production in Europe being very low, about 5,000 ha (Tittatelli et al., 2016). From a farmer's
60 perspective, conversion to organic greenhouse production has still risks. Except of general
61 agronomical drawbacks such as the lower annual yields per area, the need for adequate supply of
62 water and nutrients (under the provision of Nitrates Directive), limitations in crop protection as no
63 chemical compounds are allowed and other. Especially for plant diseases, where the prevention of
64 the infection is usually the only way to cope with the disease, the application of broad-spectrum
65 copper-based fungicides, is widely used.

66 Nevertheless, based on the EU regulations, even copper (Cu) is considered as a contentious input
67 in organic farming. In organic tomato, that covers almost 50% of the cultivated organic greenhouse
68 area, Cu is applied in standard scheduled applications up to the maximum allowed quantities that
69 were up to 6 kg Cu ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, for the control of fungi diseases such as early blight (*Alternaria*
70 *tomatophila* and *A. solani*), late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*), *Xanthomonas* spp., *Pseudomonas*
71 spp, *Cladosporiosis* and *Botrytis* disease (Katsoulas et al., 2020). According to the latest EC
72 regulation, the upper limit was recently reduced to 4 kg Cu ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. Thus, alternative approaches
73 for rational disease suppression are needed, in both organic and conventional farming, in order to
74 reduce the use of contentious inputs and plant protection products.

75 Grey mould or simply *Botrytis* disease on tomato is caused by the fungus *Botrytis cinerea* (*B.*
76 *cinerea*), one of the most common phytopathogenic fungi that affects a wide range of greenhouse
77 crops and can dramatically reduce greenhouse production and post-harvest commercial value of
78 the products (Dik and Wubben, 2007). The different life stages of the infection pathway of *B.*
79 *cinerea* are fully dependent on local microclimatic conditions and are sensitive to environmental
80 extremes. The pathogen infects leaves, stems, flowers, and fruits (Elad and Shtienberg, 1995).

81 High relative humidity in the greenhouse and free moisture on plant surfaces are considered the
82 most important environmental factors which influence infection by *B. cinerea* and other species of
83 *Botrytis* (Blakeman 1980).

84 The main strategy of greenhouse (and open field) growers to prevent or suppress infections from
85 *B. cinerea*, is to spray the aboveground parts of plants (Elad and Shtienberg, 1995) mainly with
86 protective mode of action fungicides under a routine timetable (often weekly), in rates that range
87 from one to twenty treatments per growing season, whether the need of fungicides is necessary
88 or not (Leroux, 2007). The development of resistant strains of *B. cinerea* to many botryticides, a
89 serious drawback to chemical control of the disease (Hahn, 2014), together with the negative
90 public perception regarding the safety of pesticides and the restricted use of new and established
91 fungicides, increases the need for alternative and preventive crop protection methods.

92 The relation of *Botrytis* infection pathway to the environment became a target for the scientists in
93 order to indirectly control the disease. Weather-based disease models that predict the incidence
94 of *Botrytis* were implemented for field crops (Bulger et al., 1987; Vincelli and Lorbeer, 1989;
95 Tronsmo, 1991; Broome et al. 1995; Bastiaansen et al., 1997; Shtienberg and Elad, 1997; de Kraker
96 et al., 1999; Xu et al., 2000; de Kraker et al., 2005) and focus on the integration of chemical,
97 biological and non-chemical measures to the management of *B. cinerea*. In addition, early
98 detection of plant diseases by innovative technologies such as remote sensing (e.g. Rumpf et al.,
99 2010) or cloud based DSSs (Rupnik et al., 2019) have also been proposed. Pavan et al. (2011),
100 evaluated different predictive models for *Anthraco*se and *Botrytis* fruit rot diseases and
101 developed a web-based tool for use by growers to schedule their fungicide applications, which
102 reduced the number of sprays by about 50%. The models utilized leaf wetness and temperature
103 during the wet period to predict disease outbreaks.

104 In greenhouses, Yunis et al. (1990) studied the effect of air temperature, relative humidity, and
105 canopy wetness on *Botrytis* in cucumber while Yunis et al. (1994) developed a model to predict
106 outbreaks of *Botrytis* in cucumber using outside weather data and produced multilinear
107 correlations between *Botrytis* incidence and duration of air temperature and relative humidity in
108 certain ranges, and leaf wetness. Shtienberg and Elad (1997) developed a strategy to help decide
109 whether to spray a biocontrol agent or a fungicide, based on outside weather data, for cucumber
110 and tomato greenhouses. Clarke et al. (1999) presented a DSS for integrated crop management of
111 greenhouse cucumber and tomato. The approach of the DSS of de Kraker et al. (1999) and de
112 Kraker et al. (2000) was based on models of *Botrytis* epidemiology, and the actions proposed were
113 focused more on applications of fungicides rather than in preventive farm management strategies.
114 Tantau and Lange (2003) developed the basics of a computer-supported, anti-*Botrytis* climate
115 control management for a fuchsia crop based on energy and mass transport processes modelling
116 within the canopy, the exchange processes between air and plant elements and other surfaces.
117 Their model was focused more on aiding the decision for fungicide applications.

118 Körner and Holst (2005) used a mathematical model which calculates leaf wetness duration and
119 leaf dryness to optimise climate control for energy saving and *Botrytis* prevention in

120 chrysanthemum. They used the model to perform simulations with a set of yearly reference
121 climate data of Denmark and calculated periods of condensation on leaves and according to that,
122 the greenhouse climate was controlled to a relative safe humidity level by ventilation and heating
123 to avoid *B. cinerea* incidence, something that led to estimations of high amounts of energy saving.
124 [Baptista et al. \(2012\)](#) investigated the effect of ventilation management on the environmental
125 conditions and on the disease severity of *Botrytis*. Based on the study, they developed a warning
126 system to help to decide on appropriate actions and correct timing to avoid conditions that favour
127 disease development based on air relative humidity values.

128 [De Visser et al. \(2015\)](#), presented a DSS which is based on past and real time data input from the
129 climate computer of the greenhouse to predict spore pressure and risk on *Botrytis* infection in
130 greenhouse tomato. They included dynamic models on tomato plant growth, plant energy balance
131 and fungal development to predict the disease risk as a function of climate and state of crop and
132 spore pressure and develop advises for the grower to make climate related decisions to prevent
133 *Botrytis* infections. Nevertheless, for the future predictions, a standard weather year was used to
134 simulate the outdoor abiotic conditions and predict future indoor greenhouse conditions
135 favourable for disease development. [Hemming et al. \(2017\)](#), presented the development of
136 'Roaming Climate Measuring Box' and 'Botrytis Alert', web-based decision support models that
137 give insight in the climate distribution and predict the risk for botrytis based on online
138 measurements of temperature and humidity distribution inside a greenhouse. The greenhouse
139 climate is automatically controlled based on the most humid or coldest spot in the greenhouse,
140 minimising in this way the risk for botrytis on the crop.

141 [Cañadas et al. \(2017\)](#) described a real-time decision support system for greenhouse tomatoes that
142 supports decisions at three stages – the supervision stage that identifies climate sensor faults, the
143 control stage that maintain climate variables at setpoints, and the strategic stage that identifies
144 diseases affecting the crop and changes climate variables accordingly to minimize damage.

145 Nevertheless, as presented above and to the authors' best knowledge, most of the systems
146 available make use of the current, near past or historical data to produce an assessment for the
147 development of the disease. However, as for most fungi, the prevention of the infection is more
148 effective than to combat the spread of the disease ([Shtienberg, 2007](#)), it is important to produce
149 and make available in advance predictions for future risk assessment of the disease and early
150 warnings for the grower to take decisions to act.

151 Thus, aim of this study is to design a Decision Support System (DSS) for the control of *Botrytis*
152 disease on greenhouse tomato crops that will predict in advance the development of the disease.
153 *Botrytis* disease models available in the literature will be used to predict the risk of the incidence
154 and development of the disease in the greenhouse.

155

156

157 **2. Theory- Disease development conditions and modelling**

158 The development of *Botrytis* fungi has been correlated to the microclimate conditions
159 surrounding the crop. Thus, some studies determined the limit values (thresholds) of the
160 microclimate parameters that are necessary for the completion of a stage of the infection pathway
161 of the fungus, while others developed disease models that incorporate the above-mentioned
162 microclimatic parameters to estimate the possibility of *Botrytis* disease development.

163 The infection process of a host tissue begins with the germination of the conidium (spore) that is
164 deposited on the host tissue, a process directly related to the local abiotic microenvironment
165 (boundary layer) of the plant tissue. As *B. cinerea*'s conidia contain very little water and the rest
166 needed for their germination must be absorbed by their environment, free water in the
167 surrounding microenvironment of the plant tissue is essential for rapid conidial germination and
168 infection (Jarvis, 1980; Elad and Yunis, 1993; Körner and Holst, 2005). After the germination of
169 conidia, a root-like structure called appressorium is developed, with which the fungus penetrates
170 the host tissue and enters inside the host. During this time range of germination and growth of
171 conidia outside the host, the fungus is sensitive to microclimate conditions that determine the
172 disease development rate (Tantau and Lange, 2003). Conidia may also enter inside the hostplant
173 directly from an open fresh wound (Holz et al., 2007). After the fungus enters inside the host,
174 begins the development of the fungus mycelium, with the simultaneous death of the host tissue.
175 Under humid conditions, the mycelium begins to sporulate and produce structures called
176 conidiophores in which new conidia are developed. The rate of sporulation depends on the humid
177 conditions of the outer environment, while the release and dispersal of conidia happen after a
178 sudden drop of air humidity (de Visser et al., 2015). Finally, the presence of plant debris inside the
179 greenhouse, increase the possibility of the presence of resistant life stages of the fungus like
180 sclerotia, that when the conditions will become favourable, will sprout, and produce
181 conidiophores and conidia and start new generations of infections.

182

183 *2.1 Disease development conditions*

184 In greenhouse environments, conidia of *B. cinerea* are always present (Kerssies, 1994). The
185 inoculum may originate from the greenhouse itself or may be introduced from a distance (streams
186 of air coming from outside, grafting implements or knives that contaminate plants while being
187 used).

188 The infection process involves three consecutive phases: germination, penetration and
189 establishment (Goodman et al. 1986). During the two first phases the disseminated conidia and
190 newly germinated conidia are extremely sensitive to microclimatic influences (Tantau and Lange,
191 2003). In the last phase, however, the mycelium is affected by the conditions prevailing within the
192 host tissue. The main difference between these two environments is the accessibility of free water
193 (Elad and Shtienberg, 1995).

194 The infection process of a host tissue begins with the germination of the conidium (spore) that is
195 deposited on the host tissue, a process directly related to the local abiotic microenvironment
196 (boundary layer) of the plant tissue (Köhl et al. 2007).

197 The presence of free water on the surface of the crop tissue, where conidia are deposited, is
198 essential for conidial germination and increases the “*probability of infection*”. Free water becomes
199 available on plant surfaces when high humidity conditions occur in the microclimate of the plant,
200 usually when the air relative humidity exceeds 95% or the air vapour pressure deficit (D_i) is lower
201 than 0.2 kPa or the crop-to-air vapour pressure deficit (D_{i-c}) is lower than 0.4 kPa (Körner and
202 Holst, 2005). Also, free water on the surface of a plant tissue can be provided by condensation of
203 air water vapour on a plant part that is colder than the surrounding air dew point temperature.

204 The fungus conidia deposited on a plant tissue covered by a layer of free water, need a minimum
205 wetness period (W) to absorb water and complete the normal processes for their germination. If
206 this wetness period is not completed or if it is interrupted before completed, the conidia do not
207 germinate. The needed W depends also on temperature. Provided that there is a film of water on
208 the surface of the host, germination occurs at a wide range of temperatures between 2°C and 30°C
209 (Elad and Yunis, 1993), with 9°C to 22°C being the optimum temperatures for conidia germination
210 and infection (Jarvis, 1980). When the conidia of *B. cinerea* were exposed to free water on the
211 surface of the tissue, their germination began after incubation of 4 hours at 22°C; and the rate of
212 tissue infection increased by increasing the duration of tissue wetness at all temperatures (Körner
213 and Holst, 2005). A minimum W of 4 h is determined as the shortest period that conidia need to
214 germinate at the optimum temperature regime. Thus, the duration of 4 h will be used in this study
215 as a strict threshold for W . Below this W value, it will be considered that there will be no conidia
216 germination, thus no infection will occur.

217 The infection of *Botrytis* at specific climate conditions is completed when the conidia have fully
218 germinated and penetrated the host tissue. How slow or how rapid this process of the infection is,
219 determines the “*disease development rate*”. Some studies have determined the limit values
220 (thresholds) of the microclimate parameters that are necessary for the completion of a stage of
221 the infection pathway of the fungus. Conidia of *B. cinerea* require a film of water on the surface of
222 the crop tissue where they are deposited for germination and germ tube growth (Carre and Coyier
223 1984). The development rate of *B. cinerea* depends directly on the air humidity values around the
224 host tissue that have to be high (>85%); and the air temperature (Tantau and Lange, 2003). The
225 fungus conidia deposited on a plant tissue covered by a layer of free water, need a minimum
226 wetness period (W) to absorb water and complete the normal processes for their germination.
227 When the critical leaf wetness period is met, the disease incidence increases with increasing
228 duration of tissue wetness at all temperatures (Körner and Holst, 2005). The needed W depends
229 also on temperature. Provided that there is a film of water on the surface of the host, germination
230 occurs at a wide range of temperatures between 2°C and 30°C (Elad and Yunis, 1993), with 9°C to
231 22°C being the optimum temperatures for conidia germination and infection (Jarvis, 1980). When
232 spores were exposed to free water, germination was initiated at 22°C after 4 h of incubation and

233 50% of the conidia germinated after approximately 7 h and 95% after 11 h (Carre and Coyier
234 1984). If this wetness period is not completed or if it is interrupted before completed, the conidia
235 do not germinate. Also, spores are sensitive to desiccation and die after long low humidity
236 conditions in the order of 60% RH (Nederhoff, 1997), but after short periods of dryness (less than 2
237 hours) spores continue germinating when leaf wetness occurs again (Nederhoff, 1997) and this
238 effect is cumulative (Eden et al., 1996). As a minimum W of 4 h is determined as the shortest
239 period that conidia need to germinate at the optimum temperature regime (Carre and Coyier
240 1984), this duration of 4 h will be used in this study as a strict threshold for W . Below this W value,
241 it will be considered that there will be no conidia germination, thus no infection will occur. The
242 duration of infection may last from 6 h (4 h the spore germination process and 2 h the host tissue
243 penetration) at very moist environments, to 96 h, at less moist situations (Carre and Coyier 1984).
244 If during the above period, a period of dry events occurs, the drying effect results in a prolonged
245 duration until infection. Yet, the total duration cannot be more than 4 days or 96 h, when longer
246 the spores die.

247 The number of conidia produced from an infected tissue and the rate of sporulation, determines
248 the “spore pressure” for the disease, meaning the presence of conidia and the rate of dispersal and
249 spread of the disease. The rate of sporulation of *B. cinerea* established in infected tissues, has a
250 narrow range of optimum temperatures of about 13-17°C. Low conidia production occur at
251 temperatures below 10°C or above 22°C. In infected hosts, abundant sporulation occurs at air
252 relative humidity levels above 85%.

253 Finally, the release of the conidia after sporulation initiates the dispersal of the disease. The
254 conidiophores where conidia are created, need a sudden drop of air relative humidity to break
255 their outer shell, release the conidia of *B. cinerea* and disperse them to the environment of the
256 greenhouse.

257

258 2.2 Disease modelling

259 To evaluate the risk for *Botrytis* disease in greenhouses, this work uses models of *Botrytis*
260 epidemiology available in the literature that refer to *Botrytis* spore germination and sporulation,
261 processes of infection of *Botrytis* that are related strictly to the microclimate of the greenhouse,
262 and evaluates them for tomato crops, since the basic requirements and influencing factors for
263 *Botrytis* spore germination may be considered as common for most crops.

264 A few models are already available in the literature and incorporate the effects of climate
265 parameters on the process of fungus infection or growth and predict the probability of *Botrytis*
266 disease development in the open field. However, the use of these models under greenhouse
267 climate conditions is rare. In this work, the model developed by Broome et al. (1995) is adopted to
268 predict the probability of disease development based on the wetness period (W) under different
269 temperature regimes. In addition, the disease development rate is estimated based on the model
270 proposed by Tantau and Lange (2003) and the spore production density is estimated as proposed

271 by de Visser et al. (2010) in relation with day and night-time vapour pressure deficit. The brief
 272 description of these models is given in the next sub-sections.

273

274 2.2.1. Probability of infection

275 Broome et al. (1995) developed a multiple regression model that describes the logit P , meaning
 276 the probability of infection by *B. cinerea* as a function of wetness duration (W , in h) and air
 277 temperature (T_i , in °C). The result of the logit (P) of the equation, represents the relative risk of
 278 infection:

$$P = \ln(Z/(1-Z)) = b_0 + b_1W + b_2W T_i + b_3W T_i^2 \quad (1)$$

279 where Z is the proportion of the diseased host. The values of the constants b_0 , b_1 and b_2 were
 280 taken as given in Broome et al. (1995) ($b_0=-2.4189$, $b_1=-0.1244$, $b_2=0.0416$ and $b_3=-0.0011$). The
 281 result of equation (1) indicates the relative probability of infection as follows:

- 282 – If $0.01 < P < 0.5$, then a low risk is indicated
- 283 – If $0.5 < P < 1$, then a moderate risk is indicated
- 284 – If $1.0 < P$, then a high risk is indicated

285 The calculation of P stops if a dry period of more than 4 hours occurs. If within 4 hours of a dry
 286 period a new wet period occurs, then the accumulation of wetness duration hours resumes.

287

288 2.2.2. Disease development rate

289 Tantau and Lange (2003) quantified the dependence of humidity expressed in terms of vapour
 290 pressure deficit at a given air temperature on the development rate of the infection process of *B.*
 291 *cinerea*, meaning the germination and growth of spores (conidia) and the penetration of the host
 292 tissue. After the fungus is established, high humidity stimulates the rapid mycelial growth of the
 293 fungus. The equations used in this work to calculate the disease development rate (Y , in h^{-1}) are
 294 given in Table 1.

295

296

297

298 **Table 1.** Relation of *Botrytis* disease development rate with the air vapour pressure deficit (D_i , in
 299 kPa) under different air temperature (T_i , in °C) regimes, as given in Tantau and Lange (2003).

Temperature regime	Disease development rate (Y)
$T_i < 19^\circ\text{C}$ or $T_i > 26^\circ\text{C}$	$Y = -2.3367*(D_i/10)^2 + 0.2944*(D_i/10) + 0.7116$ (2)
$19^\circ\text{C} < T_i < 21^\circ\text{C}$ or $23^\circ\text{C} < T_i < 25^\circ\text{C}$	$Y = -1.622*(D_i/10) + 1.1615$ (3)

21°C < T_i < 23°C

$$Y = -0.2913 * (D_i/10)^2 - 1.2289 * (D_i/10) + 1.1654 \quad (4)$$

300

301 If the estimated Y value is higher than 0.3 h⁻¹, a high rate of disease development is indicated.

302

303 2.2.3. Spore pressure

304 The spore pressure is estimated following the approach suggested by [de Visser et al. \(2010\)](#) that
305 correlated the spore production intensity (SPI) with the air vapour pressure deficit, with night (D_{i-n})
306 and daytime (D_{i-d}) air vapour pressure deficit having a different impact:

$$SPI = -0.2816 * D_{i-d} - 2.3583 * D_{i-n} + 0.2572 * N_{NH} \quad (5)$$

307 where D_{i-d} and D_{i-n} are the mean daytime and night-time air vapour pressure deficit respectively
308 and N_{NH} is the number of night hours. The number of spores (conidia) produced per m² during 24
309 hours (spore production density, SPD) is then calculated as:

$$SPD = [SPI / (0.061 - 0.037 * SPI + 0.046 * SPI^{0.5})] / 78.5 * 10^{-4} \quad (6)$$

310

311 2.3. Greenhouse microclimate modelling

312 The values of the greenhouse microclimate (air temperature, air relative humidity and vapour
313 pressure deficit) and crop (leaf wetness period) variables that are needed as input in the disease
314 model were estimated based on the simplified greenhouse climate model presented in [Boulard
315 and Baille \(1993\)](#) that is briefly resumed in the following sub-sections and the outside climate
316 conditions.

317

318 2.3.1. Greenhouse air temperature and air relative humidity

319 If the characteristic parameters of the greenhouse (η : greenhouse solar efficiency, dimensionless;
320 τ : greenhouse transmittance to solar radiation, dimensionless; K_c : overall heat transfer coefficient
321 of the cover material, W m⁻² °C⁻¹), the coefficients for ventilation heat exchange (K_s , K_l : the
322 coefficients of sensible and latent heat exchange by ventilation, respectively, W m⁻² °C⁻¹) and the
323 coefficients for crop heat exchange (α , a , b : the canopy absorption coefficient for solar radiation,
324 dimensionless; function of the canopy aerodynamic resistance s m⁻¹; and function of the canopy
325 stomatal resistance, s m⁻¹; respectively) are known, the air temperature (T_i , °C) and air vapour
326 pressure (e_i , kPa) inside the greenhouse can be estimated, based on outside weather conditions,
327 meaning the outside global radiation (G_o , W m⁻²), the outside air temperature (T_o , °C) the outside
328 air vapour pressure (e_o , kPa) and vapour pressure deficit (D_o , kPa), as follows ([Boulard and Baille,
329 1993](#)):

330
$$T_i = T_o + \left[\left(\frac{b+K_l}{K_l} \eta G_o \right) - bD_o - a\alpha\tau G_o \right] / \left[b\delta(T_o) + \frac{(b+K_l)(K_s+K_c)}{K_l} \right] \quad (7)$$

331 and

332
$$e_i = e_o + [\eta G_o - \Delta T (K_s + K_c)] / K_l \quad (8)$$

333 where δ is the slope of the water vapour saturation curve at T_o (kPa °C⁻¹), and ΔT is the greenhouse
 334 to outside air temperature difference (°C). The coefficient of ventilation sensible heat exchange
 335 can be estimated as follows:

336
$$K_l = (\gamma \rho \lambda V_g N) / 3600 S_g \quad (9)$$

337 where γ is the conversion factor between the water vapour content (kg_{water} kg_{air}⁻¹) and the air
 338 water vapour pressure (kPa) (kg_{water} kg_{air}⁻¹ kPa⁻¹), ρ is the air density (kg_{air} m⁻³), λ is the latent heat
 339 of vaporization (kJ kg⁻¹ °C⁻¹), V_g is the greenhouse volume (m³), S_g is the ground area (m²), N is the
 340 air exchange rate (h⁻¹). The greenhouse air exchange rate can be estimated as follows:

341
$$N = [\zeta (S_o/2) C^{0.5} u] (3600 S_g / V_g) \quad (10)$$

342 where ζ is the discharge coefficient of the vent openings of the greenhouse (dimensionless), C is
 343 the wind coefficient of the vent openings of the greenhouse (dimensionless), S_o is the ratio of the
 344 surface of vent openings (S_v , m²) to greenhouse ground (S_g , m²) area (m² m⁻²) and u is the outside
 345 air velocity (m s⁻¹).

346 Then, the sensible heat exchanges by ventilation can be estimated as follows:

347
$$K_s = (\rho C_p V_g N) / (3600 S_g) \quad (11)$$

348 where C_p is the air thermal capacity.

349 The overall energy loss coefficient can be estimated as $K_c = A + B u$, where A and B are constants that
 350 are related to greenhouse cover and air leakages.

351 The greenhouse air relative humidity can be derived by the ratio of the greenhouse air vapour
 352 pressure to the greenhouse air vapour pressure at saturation at T_i , while the greenhouse air
 353 vapour pressure deficit can be estimated by the difference of the greenhouse air vapour pressure
 354 from the greenhouse air vapour pressure at saturation at T_i .

355

356

357 2.3.2. Greenhouse crop temperature and wetness duration

358 The crop temperature (T_c), can be estimated from the sensible energy balance of the crop [Boulard
 359 et al. (1993)]:

360
$$T_c = T_i + [r_a (a \tau G_o - \lambda E_t) / \rho C_p L] \quad (12)$$

361 where r_a is the leaf aerodynamic resistance (two faces in parallel, $s\ m^{-1}$), L is the leaf area index (m^2
362 m^{-2}) and λE_t is the canopy transpiration rate ($W\ m^{-2}$) estimated as:

363
$$\lambda E_t = K_l \Delta e \quad (13)$$

364 where Δe is the greenhouse to outside air vapour pressure difference (kPa).

365 If the estimated crop temperature is lower than the greenhouse air dew point temperature, then it
366 is considered that condensation will take place in the surface of the leaves. Based on the above
367 assumption, the wetness duration is estimated.

368 The canopy-to-air vapour pressure deficit can be estimated by the difference of the greenhouse air
369 vapour pressure from the air vapour pressure at saturation at T_c .

370

371 **3. Materials and Methods**

372 The system is hosted in the UTH-Clima web-based greenhouse information and decision support
373 system (<http://www.uth-clima.eu>) that was developed to provide to registered greenhouse
374 growers and extension agents with tools aiming to aid their decision-making in relation, among
375 others, to microclimate and crop management towards the reduction of plant protection
376 products.

377

378 *3.1. Development of the DSS*

379 The DSS is working based on the following approach/steps:

380 (1) retrieval of outside weather predictions for the future 5 days for the location of the
381 greenhouse,

382 (2) estimation of the future climate conditions inside the greenhouse based on the outside climate
383 forecasted, the greenhouse climate model (see section 2.3) and the climate control settings for
384 heating, ventilation, dehumidification, and cooling,

385 (3) the estimated greenhouse climate data from step (2) are used to:

386 (a) assess the disease development risk based on the microclimate parameters' (air
387 relative humidity, air, and canopy-to-air vapor pressure deficit and leaf wetness duration)
388 thresholds related to the disease development conditions (see section 2.1), and

389 (b) assess the disease development based on disease modelling (see section 2.2) and
390 disease risk indices,

391 (4) according to the results of steps (3a) and (3b), the system proposes possible actions that a
392 grower could take in advance to avoid or control the development of the disease.

393

394 Step (1): Weather forecasts are retrieved in daily basis in XML format from the weather server
395 Dark Sky and include the following outside climate parameters: air temperature, air relative
396 humidity and velocity, solar radiation and cloudiness. The forecast concerns the weather data of
397 the next 5 days, so that the climate inside the greenhouse for the future 5 days could be
398 estimated.

399 Step (2): In order to estimate the greenhouse microclimate and crop parameters, the model
400 presented in section 2.3 is used. The model is running every hour and uses as input the outside
401 weather forecast. The output of the model is then adjusted based on the climate control settings
402 of the greenhouse. These settings include: the heating temperature set point (if the greenhouse is
403 equipped by a heating system), the ventilation temperature set point and the cooling temperature
404 set point (if the greenhouse is equipped with cooling). Then, if the greenhouse air temperature

405 estimated by the model is below the heating temperature set point, the system assumes that the
406 heating set point is always obtained. If the greenhouse air temperature estimated is above the
407 ventilation set point, then a relevant vent opening is estimated and considered for the correction
408 of the estimated microclimate values. Finally, if the greenhouse air temperature estimated is
409 above the cooling set point, then the system assumes that cooling set point is always obtained.
410 The same approach is considered if the greenhouse is equipped with a dehumidification system.
411 The above greenhouse climate control settings are introduced in a relevant tab of the web-based
412 system. Furthermore, in a different tab, the greenhouse and crop related constants (e.g.,
413 greenhouse covered area, transmission to solar radiation, vent opening area, etc) needed for the
414 model to run, are introduced. The user can also enter some additional parameters/observations
415 concerning the presence of *Botrytis* or other diseases or insects on the crop that could be crucial
416 for plants' health. It can also register de-leafing and spraying dates, while can edit the cultivation
417 period settings (so that the leaf area index of the crop could be estimated). Considering that the
418 presence of other diseases or insects or that de-leafing of the plant could increase the possibility
419 for disease development, a multiplication factor can be applied on the disease risk indices so that
420 the last increase with higher rate when the above applies.

421 Step (3): To evaluate the potential risk of *Botrytis* disease development inside the greenhouse, the
422 decision support system (DSS) developed in this work, follows two approaches:

423 Step (3a): The simplest approach of the DSS to evaluate potential risk for disease development is
424 based on the threshold values of certain relevant parameters of the greenhouse and crop
425 microclimate, as presented in section 2.1. These microclimatic parameters are the: air and canopy
426 temperature, air relative humidity, air, and canopy-to-air vapour pressure deficit and leaf wetness
427 duration. If the values of the above parameters, as predicted using the models presented in
428 section 2.3, exceed a threshold set, then a risk for disease development is indicated. Following the
429 literature survey presented in section 2.1, two threshold values are set for each microclimate
430 parameter related to the development of the disease: a 'limit' (awareness) threshold value, aiming
431 to indicate that the microclimate parameter value predicted is close to the range of values leading
432 to development of the disease; and a 'risk' threshold value that is the lower or higher limit of the
433 range of values that are favourable for the development of the disease. Thus, each parameter can
434 be classified in three ranges of values each one leading to different disease development risk
435 levels: Level 1 (no risk level), the conditions are non-favourable for the development of the
436 disease; Level 2 (awareness level), the conditions are close to the range of values that are
437 favourable for the development of the disease; and Level 3 (high risk level), the conditions are
438 favourable for the development of the disease. The thresholds and the range of values created are
439 presented in Table 2. The limit values presented in Table 2 can be adjusted by the user in a
440 relevant tab of the user interface in the web-based platform of the DSS. A similar strategy is
441 followed for the disease risk development based on the model output values, as is presented in
442 step (3b).

443

444 **Table 2.** Threshold values set for each parameter and model output and relevant risk levels
 445 defined.

Parameter or model output	Risk Level			Reference
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	
RH_i (%)	$RH_i < 85$	$85 < RH_i < 92$	$92 < RH_i$	Tantau and Lange (2003)
D_i (kPa)	$0.6 < D_i$	$0.2 < D_i < 0.6$	$D_i < 0.2$	Körner and Holst (2005)
D_{i-c} (kPa)	$0.6 < D_{i-c}$	$0.4 < D_{i-c} < 0.6$	$D_{i-c} < 0.4$	Körner and Holst (2005)
T_c (°C)	$T_{dew} + 0.5 < T_c$	$T_{dew} - 0.5 < T_c < T_{dew} + 0.5$	$T_c < T_{dew} - 0.5$	Zhang et al. (1997)
W (min)	$W < 120$	$120 < W < 240$	$240 < W$	Elad et al. (1992)
P (dimensionless)	$0.01 < P < 0.5$	$0.5 < P < 1.0$	$1.0 < P$	Broome et al. (1995)
Y (h^{-1})	$Y = 0$	$Y < 0.3$	$Y > 0.3$	Tantau and Lange (2003)
SPD (conidia $m^{-2} d^{-1}$)	$SPD < 1700$	$1700 < SPD < 5000$	$SPD > 5000$	de Visser et al. (2010)

446

447 Step (3b): A more complex approach is followed in this step based on the implementation of the
 448 disease models (presented in section 2.2) that take into account the effect of the microclimatic
 449 parameters in the disease development. As soon as the microclimatic parameters are estimated,
 450 disease models are run and the: (a) probability of infection, (b) disease development rate, and (c)
 451 spore production density, are estimated. Then, based on the threshold values of the above indices
 452 defined in Table 2, the relevant risk levels are estimated.

453 Step (4): According to the results of steps (3a) and (3b) and based on the risk level indicated, the
 454 system generates some suggestions for actions to the grower that may include recommendations
 455 for the management of the greenhouse microclimate and for cultivation practices to control or
 456 prevent the disease development.

457 In conclusion, based on the above description, it becomes clear that the system can estimate the
 458 disease risk indices based only on the outside weather forecast, the models described, and the
 459 user settings related to the greenhouse equipment and climate control settings, without the need
 460 of any on-site, real-time measurement.

461 The system was developed to be hosted in Windows Server platforms but it can be easily migrated
 462 to Linux/Unix operating systems. The data presented by the system are processed by proprietary

463 backend modules, implemented with Java, and are subsequently stored in a MySQL database
 464 instance. The system's web frontend is based on the Wordpress Content Management System
 465 which is extended via the use of a proprietary module (plugin) designed to retrieve and visualize
 466 the data which are saved in the MySQL database instance noted. The Wordpress plugin was
 467 elaborated using the PHP software design language, Javascript language, HTML and Cascading
 468 Style Sheets (CSS). The database is developed following a similar form, structure and technology,
 469 being supported by the MySQL, which has the ability to efficiently store, search, and retrieve data
 470 in large databases (Fraisie et al., 2006). The short-term weather forecast data of the region are
 471 automatically retrieved by the software components implemented in Java. An execution
 472 scheduling framework (Quartz) is used in order to schedule hourly and daily data retrieval. The
 473 data are then stored in the database to be used in steps (3a) and (3b). Step (3a) is executed every
 474 hour while step (3b) is automatically executed every 24 h, in a Java programming language. The
 475 generated results are presented in relevant gauges and figures to aid in fast representation of the
 476 risk assessment status and are stored in specific tabs and folders on the server (Fig. 1). A warning
 477 e-mail can be automatically sent to the registered user whenever the forecasted or recorded
 478 disease infection risk is at high-risk thresholds.

479

480 **Figure 1.** System overview.

481

482 The prototype of the web-based Greenhouse Tomato - Disease Risk Assessment System (GT-
 483 DRAS), is implemented and made available for registered users of the UTH-Clima web-based
 484 greenhouse information and decision support system.

485

486 3.2. Model validation

487 3.2.1. Greenhouse facilities, plant material and measurements

488 The greenhouse used for the validation of the greenhouse and crop microclimate model of the DSS
489 was a gothic type, multispans, polyethylene covered greenhouse. The greenhouse included six
490 adjacent, separate compartments (of 25 m × 9.6 m each, gutter height of 5 m and ridge height of
491 7.4 m), and only one of them was used for the validation of the system. The greenhouse was
492 located at the facilities of the University of Thessaly at Velestino, Greece (Longitude: 39° 22',
493 Latitude: 22° 44', 85 m).

494 A tomato crop was cultivated hydroponically in rockwool slabs in gutters hanged 0.6 m
495 aboveground with a density of 6 stems m⁻² and a leaf area index during the period of
496 measurements of about 3.5 m² m⁻².

497 A standard horticultural computer (SERCOM, The Netherlands) controlled the greenhouse
498 environment and maintained the air temperature by heating above 10°C and ventilated the
499 greenhouse whenever the greenhouse air temperature exceeded 21°C.

500 The first step to validate the tool presented herein is to make a comparison of the predicted and
501 actual microclimate and crop data observed outside and inside the greenhouse. For that reason, a
502 microclimate station was settled in the greenhouse compartment cultivated with tomato crop. The
503 station included: an air temperature and relative humidity sensor, four leaf temperature sensors, a
504 leaf wetness sensor and a solar radiation sensor. In addition, a station measuring air temperature,
505 air relative humidity and velocity, and solar radiation outside the greenhouse was also used. Based
506 on the above data, the air and canopy-to-air vapour pressure deficit, as well as the dew point
507 temperature and the wetness duration period were calculated (Table 3).

508 Data recording takes place every 5 minutes. Recorded and estimated data are uploaded
509 automatically on the web server and are presented online in text, graphic and image format, on
510 the web platform, hosted on www.uth-clima.eu (Fig. 1).

511 Thus, although the DSS does not need real time on-site climate data recordings for the estimation
512 of the disease risk indices, the web platform can be connected to a climate station that can record
513 the real time data of the climate inside and outside the greenhouse. The greenhouse microclimate
514 data recorded, and the outside and greenhouse microclimate data predicted are stored in the
515 database of the system and presented in the data view tabs of the web-page view of the DSS as
516 text or graphics. This provides to users the capacity to verify the weather conditions related with
517 simulated risk levels. The information may be also useful to the greenhouse manager and decision-
518 makers to assist in the interpretation and understanding of the weather conditions associated with
519 the disease. The component presents weather variables such as air temperature, air relative
520 humidity, crop temperature, dew point temperature, vapour pressure deficit, leaf wetness
521 duration and other measured or estimated parameter, for any past date or for the next 5 days.

522

523 **Table 3.** Measured and calculated data inside and outside the greenhouse

	DATA TYPE	SYMBOL	UNIT	ACCURACY	
MEASURED	Inside	Air temperature	T_i	°C	0.1° C
		Air Relative humidity	RH_i	%	0.1 %
		Crop temperature	T_c	°C	0.01° C
		Leaf wetness		%	0.01%
		Solar radiation	G_i	W m ⁻²	0.1 W m ⁻²
	Outside	Air temperature	T_o	°C	0.1°C
		Air Relative humidity	RH_o	%	0.1%
		Solar radiation	G_o	W m ⁻²	0.1 W m ⁻²
		Wind speed	u	m s ⁻¹	0.01 m s ⁻¹
		CALCULATED	Inside	Air vapour pressure deficit	D_i
Canopy-to-air vapour pressure deficit	D_{r-c}			kPa	
Dew Point Temperature	T_{dew}			°C	
Wetness Duration	W			min	
Outside	Air vapour pressure deficit		D_o	kPa	

524

525 3.2.2. Validation

526 The hourly microclimate data forecasted for the location of the greenhouse were compared with
527 those measured outside the greenhouse. In addition, the mean hourly outside weather data
528 measured during the experimental period were used as input to the model to calculate the
529 microclimate conditions inside the greenhouse. The results were compared with the actual
530 conditions measured in the greenhouse. The accuracy of the model was assessed based on the
531 root mean square error values (RMSE).

532

533

534 **3. Results**

535

536 *3.1. Validation of the outside weather forecast*

537 The time course of measured (by the greenhouse weather station) and forecasted (by the weather
538 forecast service of Dark Sky Company as given in www.darksky.net) air temperature, air relative
539 humidity, solar radiation and wind speed values outside the greenhouse during 7 consecutive days
540 (19 January 2020 – 25 January 2020) is shown in Figure 2.

541

542

543

(a)

544

545

(b)

546

547

(c)

548

549

(d)

550 **Figure 2.** Time course of measured (—) and predicted (- -) microclimate values outside the
 551 greenhouse during 7 consecutive days (19 January 2020 – 25 January 2020). (a) air temperature;
 552 (b) air relative humidity; (c) solar radiation; (d) air velocity.

553

554 The forecast predictions are in good agreement both at level and time course with the measured
 555 air temperature as well as air relative humidity values outside of the greenhouse. The largest
 556 difference between forecasted and measured air temperature and relative humidity values
 557 outside the greenhouse, 1.7°C and 18%, respectively, were observed mainly during periods with
 558 rapid change of the climate variables (early morning and late afternoon). The average daytime
 559 (08:00-17:00) values of forecasted air temperature and relative humidity during the 7 days period

560 were 8.9°C and 56%, while the corresponding measured values were 9.5°C and 59%. The
561 corresponding night-time average values (18:00-07:00) of forecasted air temperature and relative
562 humidity were 5.1°C and 73%, while the corresponding measured values were 5.7°C and 77%. The
563 root mean square error values (RMSE) estimated for the air temperature and air relative humidity
564 values during the 7 days period were 0.8°C and 7%, respectively.

565 Concerning the solar radiation, the forecasted values are in very good agreement with the
566 measured ones with few differences observed during the midday of partially cloudy days. The
567 average forecasted solar radiation value during the 7 days period was 247 W m⁻², while the
568 corresponding average measured value was 228 W m⁻². The RMSE value estimated for the solar
569 radiation during the 7 days period was 64 W m⁻².

570 In relation to the wind speed values, the forecast is also able to predict the time course of
571 measured wind speed, but the level of the forecasted values is many times much higher than the
572 measured one. This could be due to the fact that the predicted values correspond to the level of
573 10 m height and no adjustment was made to the level of the greenhouse microclimate station. In
574 addition, the forecast cannot take into account the detailed morphology of the location while the
575 observed values may be affected by the surrounding trees and buildings. The largest differences
576 observed during periods with high air velocities. The RMSE value estimated for the wind speed
577 values during the 7 days period was 1.4 m s⁻¹.

578

579 *3.2. Validation of the greenhouse microclimate model*

580 The outside microclimate data were used as an input in the greenhouse microclimate model to
581 predict the greenhouse air and crop temperature and the greenhouse air relative humidity. The
582 time course of the measured and simulated air temperature, air relative humidity and crop
583 temperature, in the greenhouses during 6 consecutive days (19 January 2020 – 24 January 2020) is
584 shown in Figure 3.

585

586

587

588

(a)

589

590

(b)

591

592

(c)

593 **Figure 3.** Time course of measured (—) and predicted (- -) greenhouse and crop microclimate
594 values during 6 consecutive days (19 January 2020 – 24 January 2020). (a) air temperature; (b) air
595 relative humidity; (c) crop temperature.

596

597 The model can fairly simulate both the level and time course of the air and crop temperature as
598 well as the air relative humidity values inside the greenhouse. The highest differences between the
599 simulated and measured values were observed during the night time period. The average simulated
600 air and crop temperature and air relative humidity values during the 6 days period were 12.4°C,
601 13.0°C and 77%, respectively, while the corresponding measured values were 12.0°C, 13.3°C and
602 79%, respectively. The RMSE values estimated for air and crop temperature and the air relative
603 humidity values estimated by the model were 1.2°C, 1.1°C and 6%, respectively.

604 Therefore, based on the above validation results and in view also of the validation results of the
605 model already available by [Boulard and Baille \(1993\)](#), we conclude that the model fitted in the DSS
606 is suitable for the present purpose.

607

608 *3.3. Disease risk assessment*

609 The Graphical User Interphase has been developed in a way so that it could give to users a fast
610 assessment of the current risk for disease development. Thus, except of the values given, a
611 coloured indication is also included.

612 The air and crop microclimate conditions related to the development of *Botrytis* disease, namely
613 RH_i , D_i , $D_{i,c}$, $d(T_c - T_{dew})$ and W are estimated every hour for the next five days and the predicted
614 values of current time are presented in the 'Daily Overview' tab of the Graphical User Interphase
615 of the system, as shown in Fig. 4a. While the top part of Fig. 4a shows the current risk level of the
616 parameters, the bottom part presents the accumulated time of each parameter under the
617 different risk levels during a time period set by the user. The five circular gauge's sectors of the
618 above parameters indicate that the current parameter risk level may be at Level 1 (needle
619 completely to the left), Level 2 (grey and yellow) or Level 3 (orange and red). If the needle is at
620 grey or orange area it indicates that the values of the referred parameter are at Levels 2 or 3,
621 respectively, but only for a short time period. This duration of this time period is set by the system
622 manager in the system settings.

623 The set of horizontal bars in the middle of the screen indicates the time that each parameter
624 remains in each risk level. Based on the data presented in Fig. 4a, the user can see the time
625 elapsed for each parameter under the different risk levels and evaluate the potential for disease
626 development in the future.

627

Current health indices status

628

RH Running Time:	VPD Air Running Time:	VPD Crop Running Time:	LeafT-DP Running Time:	Leaf Wetness Running Time:
Caution:0min	Caution:160min	Caution:295min	Caution:0min	Caution:5min
Medium: 0min	Medium: 825min	Medium: 2050min	Medium: 0min	Medium: 0min
Critical: 0min	Critical: 0min	Critical: 0min	Critical: 0min	Critical: 5min
High: 0min	High: 0min	High: 0min	High: 0min	High: 5min

629

630

(a)

631

632

(b)

633 **Figure 4.** (a) Estimated values (and risk level) of the microclimate parameters related to the
 634 development of the disease and (b) values of the disease risk indices, as presented in the Graphical
 635 User Interphase of the DSS).

636

637 The validation of the system was further supported by evaluating its reliability in predicting the
 638 occurrence of each Risk Level for the RH , D_i , D_{i-c} , and $T_{dew}-T_c$ parameters. For this purpose,
 639 following Joliffe and Stephenson (2003), 2×2 contingency tables were produced for every Risk
 640 Level category observed in the greenhouse. Tables 3 presents the scores for the RH , D_i , D_{i-c} , and
 641 $T_{dew}-T_c$ parameters' Risk Levels, respectively.

642

643

644

645

646 Table 3. 2x2 contingency tables for each Risk Level for RH , D_i , D_{i-c} , T_{dew-T_c} (% scores) developed
 647 using the data observed during the greenhouse climate model validation (19 January 2020 – 24
 648 January 2020).

			Risk Level 1		Risk Level 2		Risk Level 3	
			Observed		Observed		Observed	
			Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
RH	Predicted	Yes	84	7	0	9	0	0
		No	9	0	7	84	0	100
D_i	Predicted	Yes	11	6	39	14	17	13
		No	1	82	14	32	17	53
D_{i-c}	Predicted	Yes	63	7	5	11	14	2
		No	6	24	8	76	5	79
T_{dew-T_c}	Predicted	Yes	99	1	0	0	0	0
		No	0	0	1	99	0	100

649

650 Table 3 shows that the true predictions [i.e. (a) observed and predicted Risk Level category and (b)
 651 not observed and not predicted Risk Level category] ranged between 84% and 100% for RH , 71%
 652 and 93% for D_i , 81% and 93% for D_{i-c} , and 99% and 100% for T_{dew-T_c} . The fact that the prediction
 653 rate is above 80% for most of the parameters and risk levels shows that the system achieved to
 654 predict well the occurrence of each Risk Level for the parameters referred in the table.

655 In addition, as shown in Fig. 4b, the system presents also the values estimated for the three
 656 disease risk indices for the last 24 hours. The 'spore production density' gauge indicates the
 657 estimated *Botrytis* spore density during the last 24 h while the 'Botrytis Development Rate' gauge
 658 indicates the current rate of *Botrytis* development risk. The AVG value from the start time until the
 659 current time is shown, with the elapsed time in minutes. Finally, the Probability of infection (P)
 660 during the period from the time set until the current time and the time duration that this
 661 probability level lasts is indicated in the box below the *Botrytis* development rate gauge.

662 The predicted length of the period that each of the crop and microclimate parameters inside the
 663 greenhouse will remain under the different risk levels during the following five days is presented in
 664 a relevant tab of the graphical user interphase (similar to the one used for the past conditions
 665 presented in Fig. 4a).

666 In addition, the spore production density estimated for each of the next five days is also shown,
 667 while the hourly values of *Botrytis* development rate and of probability of infection during the next
 668 five days are also shown.

669 Figure 5 shows the estimated values of the *Botrytis* development rate for a period of five days
 670 along with the probability of infection and the spore production density. In addition, the hourly
 671 values of the greenhouse microclimate parameters related to the development of the disease
 672 during the same time period are also presented in Fig. 5.

673

696 actions related to the modification of greenhouse microclimate that are considered to lead to
697 lower Risk Levels.

698 Several parameters and conditions are considered in order to determine the action to be
699 suggested. These are related to the number of parameters that are forecasted at Risk Levels 2 or 3
700 (Table 2), the time duration at each risk level, the occurrence of disease risk conditions in the near
701 past, the outside climate conditions, the climate control equipment of the greenhouse, the crop
702 management practices performed (e.g. de-leafing, harvesting, spraying) and possible report of
703 fungi development by the grower.

704 The specific conditions that are considered from the DSS, based on which a set of relevant actions
705 is suggest, are presented in the following subsections.

706

707 3.4.1. Reduction of greenhouse air relative humidity.

708 The greenhouse management actions suggested including methods for the reduction of
709 greenhouse air relative humidity. The aim of these actions is to avoid frequent and long periods of
710 high RH_i and low D_i inside the greenhouse. The management strategy aims to avoid conditions
711 with RH_i values above 85% for more than 6 hours. A summary of lower and upper optimal and
712 marginal D_i for greenhouse cultivation of tomato (together with T and RH) are recommended from
713 different sources in [Shamshiri et al. \(2018\)](#) and range from 0.4 to 1.20 kPa. Thus, except of the air
714 relative humidity, the DSS takes into account the air temperature and D_i and D_{i-c} values. It is known
715 that when the greenhouse moisture content is very high and the temperature is generally low,
716 often below 10°C, the limiting factor for infection is likely to be the temperature. The higher the
717 temperature (up to 20°C), the higher the incidence of infection ([Xu et al., 2000](#)). In addition, the
718 higher the D_i , the less favourable are the conditions for conidial survival. Pathogenic fungi survive
719 better at $D_i < 0.4$ kPa. In addition, infection by the disease is more destructive below 0.20 kPa ([Dik
720 and Wubben, 2007](#)). Thus, the greenhouse climate should be maintained at a D_i above 0.20 kPa to
721 prevent disease and damage of the crop. The initial action threshold used by the system is when
722 the predicted disease infection rate increases to 0.3 or more for more than 6 h.

723 When the predicted greenhouse RH_i is higher than the limits defined in Table 2, the grower should:

724 -dehumidify the greenhouse by means of (a) ventilation, to enable the wet air to leave outside the
725 greenhouse, provided that the absolute air humidity outside is lower than the absolute air
726 humidity inside the greenhouse or (b) dehumidification system.

727 - increase the temperature of the heating pipes (to increase the radiative part of heat dissipation
728 and thus increase the crop temperature), but not the actual greenhouse air temperature.

729 If the value of the “*disease development rate*” (Y) index indicates high risk for infection for more
730 than 6 h, it is suggested to reduce the D_i at the given T_i , by means of dehumidification.

731 If the “*spore production density*” (*SPD*) index is at a level indicating high risk during 24 h, then, as it
732 is related to D_i and is strongly affected by D_i at night hours, it is suggested to increase the D_i during
733 the night by dehumidification actions.

734 Finally, to avoid the release and dispersion of the conidia during the day, it is suggested to keep
735 RH_i values at constant levels in order to avoid sudden drops of RH_i that are necessary for the
736 release of conidia.

737

738 3.4.2. Reduction of the presence of free water on plant leaves

739 The presence of free water and the wetness duration on plant tissue (leaves or stems) are crucial
740 factors for the development of the disease. The parameters monitored by the DSS, which are
741 related to the possibility of water condensation on plant surfaces, are the crop temperature and
742 its difference with the dew point temperature ($dT_c - T_{dew}$, Table 2), the air relative humidity and the
743 duration for which RH_i exceeds 95% as well as the leaf wetness duration recorded by the relevant
744 sensor. Thus, based on the measured and estimated values of the above parameters, when there
745 is a risk of disease development due to potentially long wetness duration periods, the DSS
746 suggests the following actions to avoid free water formation on plant tissues:

747 -Use of energy screens to prevent loss of heat through radiation from the plants during the night
748 and sudden cooling of the crop (that leads to the formation of dew and free moisture on plant).

749 -When cold nights are forecasted by the DSS, heating after sunrise maintains the plants warmer
750 than their environment and thus prevents the formation of free moisture and accordingly the
751 infection of leaves and fruits.

752 - Application of heating early in the morning before the down – by a step wise increase of air
753 temperature not more than 1°C per hour.

754 In case that long wetness duration periods (W) are predicted, the DSS suggests the following
755 actions to keep the W value below a specified threshold, so that the fungus growth conditions and
756 especially conidia germination, are not favourable.

757 If the “*probability of infection*” (P) index that is related to W at a given T_i indicates low or high risk
758 for infection, then, if more than 3h of W is calculated from sensor’s data or forecasted from
759 weather data, a dry season of at least 4 hours is needed so as the process of conidia germination
760 to stop, as conidia are susceptible to drought and die. Aeration and heating regimes greatly
761 influence RH_i and W therefore prolonged humidity conditions of lower RH levels are needed. In
762 non-heated greenhouses, two important parameters associated with outbreaks of *Botrytis* incited
763 epidemics in vegetables are the W (threshold 7 h per day) and duration of night temperatures
764 between 9°C and 21°C (threshold 9.5 h per day) (Elad et al., 1992; Yunis et al., 1994). When the
765 DSS forecasts that these conditions are expected, actions of dehumidification should be taken.

766

767 3.4.3. Tactical decisions

768 When no or slow disease progress is expected, no spraying may be needed. If the practices of
769 modifying the microclimate of the greenhouse that the DSS suggests, such as actions of
770 dehumidification, greenhouse ventilation or heating are not sufficient enough to reduce the
771 parameters at high risk level after a specific duration or the P index remains at high risk level, then
772 the use of allowed protectant fungicides or biological agents in a schedule of applications is
773 suggested, together with the recommendation to alternate the various groups of alternatives, as
774 fungicide resistance of the pathogen is probable to develop and fungicide treatments will fail to
775 control the disease.

776 These actions are recommended especially if an outbreak is expected and when at least 14 days
777 have passed since the previous spraying and when the risk of disease development is high. If
778 strong sunny conditions are forecasted after prolonged dull weather, the DSS suggests the use of
779 energy screen during the day to minimize leaf burning and necrotic tissues that are vulnerable to
780 *Botrytis* infection. Also, after a predicted period with less sun (week plants) and more rain (more
781 humidity), there is greater pressure to infest, therefore there is a high need to dehumidify.

782 In non-heated greenhouses, if the average daily temperature is higher than desired, the plant will
783 be weaker and thus more susceptible to *Botrytis*. When the temperature is forecasted to be too
784 high, a change of the set points for ventilation to start may be needed.

785

786 3.4.4. Strategic decisions

787 When de-leafing is performed in the crop, pruning wounds are present acting as open gates for
788 conidia to enter and inoculate the host. When pruning wounds are present in the greenhouse, the
789 grower is recommended to increase the D_i of the greenhouse and use ventilation or use heating to
790 reduce RH , to enhance the healing of the wounds. It is also recommended to avoid harvesting
791 during wet conditions as the wounds are susceptible to infections, but if needed the application of
792 one fungicidal spray soon after the harvest is suggested.

793 Finally, the selection of plant varieties resistant or tolerant to *Botrytis* infection (if are available), is
794 a strategic decision at the beginning of the crop season, to reduce crop losses by fungus infections,
795 costs of greenhouse climate modifications and addition of chemicals to the crop.

796

797 4. Discussion

798 During the last 20 years and even earlier, several efforts have been done for *Botrytis* disease risk
799 assessment in greenhouses. Some of them were developed as a function of single measured
800 microclimate parameters within certain ranges that influence the incidence of *Botrytis* (e.g.
801 Baptista, 2007) or were based on calculated microclimate parameters and climate control
802 strategies that influence them (Tantau and Lange, 2003), others were based on modelled
803 microclimate parameters and their relevant threshold values integrated into a climate control
804 regime directly influencing the set points of the greenhouse climate control (e.g. Körner and Holst,
805 2005), while additional consider a combination of the greenhouse and crop microclimate
806 parameters to assess the disease risk based on disease development models (e.g. De Visser *et al.*,
807 2015; Körner and Holst, 2005; Cañadas *et. al.*, 2017). Most of the systems estimate the disease risk
808 based on past (e.g. Yunis *et al.*, 1994) and current microclimate data (e.g. Cañadas *et al.*, 2017),
809 others are using future weather data based on reference year weather data (e.g. Körner and Holst,
810 2005; De Visser *et al.*, 2015), while some may use actual future weather predictions to establish
811 empirical severity values reflecting the relative importance of outside weather data (e.g.
812 Shtienberg and Elad, 1997). The available systems may well differ in the degree of complexity,
813 being composed from simple databases, spreadsheets, disease simulation models or combinations
814 of tools (Shtienberg, 2013).

815 The current work takes advantage of the possibilities offered in information technology for online
816 implementation of disease development models, the delivery of site-specific weather forecasts
817 through internet and the disease epidemiology data available in the literature to develop a disease
818 risk assessment platform for prediction and management of the disease. Thus, a strong point of
819 the system presented in this work is that is based on automatic real-time prediction of *Botrytis*
820 disease incidence risk, based on real-time prediction of future weather data outside the
821 greenhouse.

822 The work combines simple disease risk indices that are based on single greenhouse and crop
823 microclimate data or disease development models which consider a combination of the above
824 climate data. This is also a strong point of the work if we consider that in most of the previews
825 works the disease risk was based mainly on one of the two approaches. In addition, the results
826 presented in Table 3 revealed that while some of the indices used (e.g. RH and $T_{dew}-T_c$) indicated
827 different risk levels than other (e.g. D_i and D_{i-c}), something that makes the combined use of the
828 simple indices presented and tested more reliable than using a single index.

829 The disease risk indices estimated relate to a decision support tool to suggest the best option
830 management practices to avoid the conditions favouring the development of the disease. The
831 options offered are oriented to preventive farm management rather than controlling the disease
832 after the outbreak.

833 However, the proposed by the DSS climate control measures are not integrated in the greenhouse
834 climate computer and the farmer has the initiative to perform the actions or not. This may be

835 considered as a weak point of the work, although the system has been developed in a way to be
836 'self-fed' with information, requiring little or no user data input. Weather data are downloaded
837 and updated automatically from weather stations into the system without the need for grower
838 involvement. The user's platform with the disease risk indices and recommendations are color-
839 coded and self-explanatory, and understandable within seconds. In case users need more detailed
840 information and complexity, it can also be found in the system.

841 The precision of a warning system based on future weather depends on two components: the
842 accuracy of the weather forecast and the validity of the decision-making process on which the
843 system is based. Validation of the decision support tool is pending and planned to be done in a
844 next work with data collected in pilot greenhouses in Greece (Volos) and Spain (Almeria).

845 Although the system is fairly validated in relation to the climate data prediction and disease risk
846 indices' reliability, it has not been validated in relation to the prediction of disease incidence. This
847 may be considered as a weak point of the work but, considering that the epidemiology models
848 integrated have been already validated in previous works, it may also be well considered that the
849 models are well functioning. The fact that the work integrates models that have not been
850 developed exclusively for tomato crop is a practice that has been followed by several authors,
851 since most of the *Botrytis* development models available make use of data presented by [Tantau](#)
852 [and Lange \(2003\)](#) and [De Visser et al. \(2010\)](#) that worked on gerbera and fuchsia crops,
853 respectively.

854 Following the above, a future challenge of this work is to use the real-time weather forecast data
855 from different regions around a country and the system presented herein to assess the potential
856 disease severity and disease dynamics and identify regions with tomato production which are
857 more susceptible for disease occurrence, as for example has been already done for early and late
858 blight in open field potato production ([Hansen et al., 2017](#)).

859

860

861 **5. Concluding Remarks**

862 This work presents the development stage of a DSS for *Botrytis* disease risk assessment in
863 greenhouse tomato crops. The efficiency of the model to predict the greenhouse microclimate
864 conditions related to the development of the disease was fairly validated. The validation of the
865 system was further supported by evaluating its reliability in predicting the occurrence the Risk
866 Levels of the greenhouse microclimate parameters related to *Botrytis* epidemiology and the
867 prediction rate observed was above 80% for most of the parameters studied.

868 The disease risk indices estimated are used as input to a module that assists in the climate
869 management of the greenhouse, by proposing preventive farm management methods to avoid the
870 conditions favouring the development of the disease. However, the proposed by the DSS climate
871 control measures are not integrated in the greenhouse climate computer and the farmer has the
872 initiative to perform the actions or not, something that may be considered as a week point of the
873 system proposed.

874 A future challenge of this work is to develop a country level disease dynamic system where, based
875 on the models incorporated in this system, the real-time weather forecast data from different
876 regions will be used to assess the potential disease severity and disease dynamics in different
877 regions for different greenhouse types and control management strategies.

878

879

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885

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892

893

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